

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SHAPE MEMORY ALLOYS

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SUMMARY: This paper reviews the three-dimensional constitutive relation of Shape Memory Alloys presented by Boyd and Lagoudas. A linear incremental constitutive equation is derived from the nonlinear one. The finite element equations in Total Lagrangian form are attained and the program is also developed. To verify the effectiveness of the program, a simple test case are examined and the result shows the reliability of the program. The finite element program is utilized to simulate the mechanical behavior of the pipe connector made by shape memory alloy, and the result of stress distribution reveals greatly unusual. Some difficulties never mentioned before are found in calculation. Measures are taken to overcome the difficulties. Since the constitutive equation of shape memory alloys is very complex, the finite element program is then shown to be a powerful tool for studying various applications of shape memory alloys.

KEYWORDS: shape memory alloys, non linear finite element program, total Lagrangian approach

INTRODUCTION

Shape memory alloys (SMA) are the alloys which have shape memory effect (SME), that means the alloys are able to sustain a large recoverable strain (of the order of 10%) without plastic deformation and to remember its initial configuration and return to it as being heated. The phenomena of SME have attracted a lot of notice of investigators since it was first observed in TiNi alloy in 1960s. Many kind of alloys, such as TiNi, Cu-based alloys, In-based alloys, austenite steels, etc., have been found to have the property of SME. The application of SMA is widely recognized not only in the science filed but also in the engineering field.

The unusual character of SMA is now known to be associated with the thermoelastic martensitic transformation and its reverse course. There are four important temperature point of the phase transformation, M_s , M_f , A_s , A_f , which denote martensite start, martensite finish, austenite start, austenite finish respectively. The martensitic fraction (ξ) is the quantity of SMA in the martensitic phase: $\xi=0$ means that the material is fully austenite, while $\xi=1$ represents that the material is fully martensite. The martensitic fraction changes as a function of temperature under stress-free conditions. More generally, the martensitic fraction is known to change as a function of both stress (S) and temperature (T). A cosine model of variety of martensitic fraction is employed. The expressions are as follows:

for austenite to martensite

$$\xi = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \cos \left[a_M (T - M_f) + b_M S_i \right] + 1 \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$a_M = \frac{\pi}{M_s - M_f}, b_M = -\frac{a_M}{c_M}$$

for martensite to austenite

$$\xi = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \cos \left[a_A (T - A_s) + b_A S_i \right] + 1 \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$a_A = \frac{\pi}{A_f - A_s}, b_A = -\frac{a_A}{c_A}$$

In Eqn 1 and Eqn 2, C_A and C_M represent material constants of SMA which determine the influence of stress on transformation temperature, and S_i is the equivalent stress.

CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONS

In this paper, the constitutive relations presented by Boyd and Lagoudas^[2] are adopted. Here we briefly review the constitutive law which will be used later.

Assuming that response will remain elastic, the three-dimensional form of the stress-strain equation may be written as

$$S^{KL} = C^{KLMN} E_{MN}^e = C^{KLMN} (E_{MN} - E_{MN}^t - \alpha_{MN} \Delta T) \quad (3)$$

where S_{KL} is the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress, E_{MN}^e , E_{MN} and E_{MN}^t are the elastic strain, the Green strain, the transformation strain, and $\Delta T = T - T_0$, where T_0 is the initial temperature. The elastic stiffness tensor C_{KLMN} and the thermoelastic expansion tensor α_{MN} are given by

$$C^{KLMN} = C_A^{KLMN} + \xi (C_M^{KLMN} - C_A^{KLMN}) \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha_{MN} = \alpha_{A_{MN}} + \xi (\alpha_{M_{MN}} - \alpha_{A_{MN}}) \quad (5)$$

The subscripts A , M denote austenite and martensite respectively.

In describing the response of SMA materials, incremental constitutive equations are required. Taking the time derivative of 3 results in the equation

$$\dot{S}^{KL} = C^{KLMN} (\dot{E}_{MN} - \dot{E}_{MN}^t - \dot{\alpha}_{MN} \Delta T - \alpha_{MN} \dot{T}) + \dot{C}^{KLMN} E_{MN}^e \quad (6)$$

The three-dimensional transformation strain rate \dot{E}_{MN}^t is obtained from

$$\dot{E}_{MN}^t = \Lambda_{MN} \dot{\xi} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\Lambda_{MN} = \begin{cases} -\frac{3}{2} \frac{\Omega}{\bar{D}} \frac{S'_{MN}}{S_i}, & \dot{\xi} > 0 \\ -\frac{\Omega}{\bar{D}} \frac{E'_{MN}}{E'_i}, & \dot{\xi} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

and where

$$E'_i = \sqrt{\frac{2}{3} E'_{MN} E'_{MN}} \quad (9)$$

$$\bar{D} = \frac{1}{2} (D_A + D_M)$$

The rates \dot{C}_{KLMN} and $\dot{\alpha}_{MN}$ may be obtained from 4 and 5 using the chain rule for the time derivative of ξ , i.e.

$$\dot{\xi} = \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial T} \dot{T} + \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial S_i} \dot{S}_i \quad (10)$$

This completes the three-dimensional SMA constitutive equations.

ONE-DIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS

In one-dimensional domain, Eqn 8 may be rewritten as

$$\Lambda = -\frac{\Omega}{D} \quad (11)$$

It has the same form for both martensitic transformation and the reverse transformation, so Eqn 7 changes to

$$E' = -\frac{\Omega}{D} \xi \quad (12)$$

Substituting the above equation into Eqn 3, one gets

$$S = D(\xi) \left(E + \frac{\Omega}{D} \xi - \alpha \Delta T \right) \quad (13)$$

Fig. 1(a). $T=A_f+50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Fig. 1(b). $T=A_f$

Fig. 1(c). $T=(A_f+A_s)/2$

Fig. 1(d). $T=A_s$

Fig.1 Stress-strain curve of SMA at various temperature

It should be noticed that if $\xi=1$ in Eqn 12, the maximum of transformation strain will be obtained, i.e.

$$E'_{\max} = -\frac{\Omega}{D}$$

which points out the physical meaning of the variable Ω .

NUMERICAL FORMULATIONS

Using the Total Lagrangian approach, the Green strain is presented as

$$E_{KL} = \frac{1}{2}(U_K|_L + U_L|_K + U_M|_K \cdot U^M|_L) \quad (14)$$

The increment of the Green strain is

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta E_{KL} &= E_{KL}^{(N+1)} - E_{KL}^{(N)} \\ &= \frac{1}{2}(\Delta U_K|_L + \Delta U_L|_K + \Delta U_M|_K \cdot U^M|_L + U_M|_K \cdot \Delta U^M|_L + \Delta U_M|_K \cdot \Delta U^M|_L)\end{aligned}\quad (15)$$

Neglecting body force, the principle of virtual work of continuous body in equilibrium, with the second Piola-Kirchhoff stress and its increment, can be written as

$$\iiint_V (S^{KL} + \Delta S^{KL}) \delta(E_{KL} + \Delta E_{KL}) dV^{(0)} - \iint_{S_\sigma} (\bar{T}^M + \Delta \bar{T}^M) \delta \Delta U_M dS^{(0)} = 0 \quad (16)$$

Substituting Eqn 15 into Eqn 16 and neglecting the higher order terms, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\iiint_V (\Delta S^{KL} \delta \Delta E_{KL}^0 + S^{KL} \Delta U_M|_K \delta \Delta U^M|_L + S^{KL} \delta \Delta E_{KL}^0) dV^{(0)} \\ - \iint_{S_\sigma} (\Delta \bar{T}^M + \bar{T}^M) \delta \Delta U_M dS^{(0)} = 0\end{aligned}\quad (17)$$

where

$$\Delta E_{KL}^0 = \frac{1}{2}(\Delta U_K|_L + \Delta U_L|_K + \Delta U_M|_K \cdot U^M|_L + U_M|_K \cdot \Delta U^M|_L)\quad (18)$$

From Eqn 6, we have

$$\Delta S^{KL} = C^{KLMN} (\Delta E_{MN} - \Delta E_{MN}^t - \alpha_{MN} \Delta T - \Delta \alpha_{MN} T) + \Delta C^{KLMN} E_{MN}^e \quad (19)$$

If we directly substitute Eqn 19 into Eqn 17, the finite element equations can be obtained. However, Eqn 19 is nonlinear and it is very difficult for numerical calculation to converge, yet it must be modified to be available for use. For convenient, here the derivation of modifying the constitutive equations is presented in the form of matrix.

Substituting Eqn 4 and Eqn 5 into Eqn 19, and using Eqn 1 and Eqn 2, Eqn 19 in the form of matrix changes as

$$\{\Delta S\} = [C][D]\{\Delta E\} - [C] \left(\{V\} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial T} + [D]\{\alpha\} \right) \Delta T \quad (20)$$

where

$$\{V\} = [D] \left[\{\Lambda\} + (\{\alpha_M\} - \{\alpha_A\})(T - T_0) \right] - ([D_M] - [D_A]) \{E^e\} \quad (21)$$

$$[C] = \left([I] + \{V\} \cdot \left\{ \frac{\partial S_i}{\partial S} \right\}^T \cdot \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial S_i} \right)^{-1} \quad (22)$$

From Eqn 17—22, the equation for finite element method is attained

$$([K_0] + [K_U] + [K_S]) \{\Delta U\} = \{\Delta Q\} + \{\Delta F\} + \{\Delta W\} \quad (23)$$

where the matrix $[K_0]$ is the incremental stiffness matrix, the matrices $[K_U]$ and $[K_S]$ are respectively the initial displacement stiffness matrix and initial stress stiffness matrix

influenced by the finite displacement, $\{\Delta Q\}$, $\{\Delta F\}$ represent the vector of applied load and the residual vector, respectively, $\{\Delta W\}$ is the vector of thermoload.

A finite element program (FEP) based on the derivation has been developed. To testify the availability of the program, a special test case is examined: a thin cylinder with internal pressure at the ratio (thickness/radius) of 1/1000. Comparison between results of FEP and the analytical one of one-dimensional case shows well agreement (Fig.2).

Fig.2(a). $T=A_f+50^\circ C$

Fig.2(b). $T=A_f$

Fig.2(c). $T=(A_f+A_s)/2$

Fig.2 (d). $T=(A_s+M_s)/2$

Fig.2 FEP result at various temperature compared with the analytical one

APPLICATION TO SMA PIPE COUPLING

One of the most established uses for shape memory alloys is that of connectors for tubing. The procedure in these applications is to manufacture a ring of shape memory alloy that has a somewhat smaller inner diameter in the austenitic state than the outer diameter of the pipes to be connected. At a temperature less than A_s the ring is then deformed and change to the martensitic state so that its inner diameter exceeds slightly that of the tubing. The ring is

placed over the pipes in this phase and then heated. As the transformation to austenite takes place, the material attempts to recover the residual strain. However, being partially restrained by the pipes, the connector subsequently recovers only part of its residual strain and finally builds up large internal stresses.

The FEP developed in this paper is utilized to simulate the whole course, add mechanical load so that the SMA connector totally transform to martensite, remove the load and the strains remained, place the connector over the pipes and warm it up. The results of stress in θ -direction of the connector and that at the SMA-pipes interface are shown in fig.3-7. with a thicker SMA connector (thickness/radius=30%)

Fig.3(a). Stress in θ -direction at the end of loading

Fig.3(b). Residual stress in θ -direction after removing load

Fig.3(c). Stress in θ -direction during heating

Fig.3 Stress of SMA in θ -direction during whole course

Fig.4 The interface stresses at various temperature
the initial temperature is 23°C , the final temperature is 151°C

Fig.5 The interface stresses at various temperature with different Young's modulus for the pipes (D_p)

Fig.6 Stress of SMA in θ -direction during heating with a thicker SMA connector (thickness/radius=30%)

Fig.7 The interface stresses at various temperature

CONCLUSION

This paper has developed a nonlinear three-dimensional axisymmetric finite element program for shape memory alloys behavior. Since the nonlinear constitutive relation is unsuitable for calculation due to the difficulties of convergence, an incremental linear constitutive relation has been proposed based on the nonlinear one, and used in the FEP.

The numerical analysis meets with some difficulties. When the SMA connector is being heated to beyond the critical temperature at which the martensite starts to transform to the austenite, the right hand side of the finite element equations changes greatly, thus bringing considerable calculation errors. It is the reason why the stresses in Fig.3(c) and Fig.6 are not smooth. To overcome the difficulties, the program is designed to be able to automatically choose a variable temperature step according to the material state. In this way, the errors of the critical step can be acceptable; meanwhile the calculation does not take too much CPU time. Another difficulty is the discontinuity of residual stress (Fig.3(c), Fig.6). When the connector is heated, the material starts to transform to Austenite. However, the reverse transformations of different points do not happen at the same time. The heterogeneous reverse transformation leads to the discontinuity of the stress in θ -direction. So the finite element meshes for calculation must be sufficiently fine to avoid the difficulties.

A special phenomenon is seen that the stress on the interface reduces while the temperature increases in some cases (Fig.7). It is induced by the large internal stresses. Since the internal stresses get greater when the thickness of SMA connector is thicker, it seems that the thickness of SMA connector should be as thin as possible to amend the interface pressure.

The results of stresses at the interface for various strengths of the pipe material are shown in Fig.5. The modulus of the pipe is much greater than that of the austenite. It is clear that the results are converging on the case of rigid pipe as one would expect.

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